

R-CURVES CHARACTERIZATION AND FAILURE DAMAGE OF SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

C. Rodriguez* and F.J.Belzunce**

* ITMA, Parque Tecnológico de Asturias, 33428 Llanera, Spain

**Dto. de Ciencia de los Materiales e Ing. Met., Universidad de Oviedo

ABSTRACT

The fracture behaviour of notched specimens of short glass fibre reinforced polyamide and polyester, with different glass weight fractions, has been characterized. The most accurate methods involve the use of the Resistance curves (R-curves), which take into account the stable crack growth which is always observed before the catastrophic failure of these materials.

In this paper, two different methods used in the determination of R-curves are analyzed, and the influence of such parameters as the notch length and acuity, the specimen size and the fibre weight fraction are also determined.

Finally, the damage developed at the process zone in front of the notch is also characterized by means of microscopic techniques, in order to assess the different micromechanisms which operate in each case.

Keywords: Plastic matrix composites, Short-fibre composites, R-curves, Toughness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites are one of the families of materials which have experienced a greater development during recent years. Short glass fibre (injection or compression moulded) reinforced plastics combine good mechanical performance with economical manufacturing costs and flexible design.

At the moment, engineers and designers need to expand their knowledge of the mechanical behaviour of these materials with regard to the critical effect of cracks and notches. Little work has been reported on the notched strength of these materials although fracture initiation at notches is a major cause of structural failure (1). The applicability of fracture mechanics techniques to solve such problems in the case of these heterogeneous materials is currently very promising.

2. MATERIALS AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

We have used four commercial sheet molding compounds (polyester resin) furnished as plates of 400x300 mm and with a thickness of 4 mm. We have also used two glass fibre reinforced polyamides (nylon 66), obtained by injection moulding of plates 150x150 mm and a thickness of 3.4 mm. Table 1 shows the main components of these materials.

	SMC1	SMC2	SMC3	SMC4		Polyamide 1	Polyamide 2
Polyester resin	24.6	53.5	38.1	28.1			
Filler (CaCO ₃)	49.3	35.3	26.9	28.1	Resin (Nylon 66)	65	50
Short glass fiber (randomly distributed)	26.1	29.4	35.0	43.8	Short glass fiber	35	50

Table 1. Materials composition, weight %

The mechanical characterization of the described materials was carried out by means of tests performed on tensile specimens 40 mm wide. Longitudinal and transversal strain gauges were used in order to obtain the elastic modulus and the Poisson ratio. Table 2 shows the obtained results.

	Elastic Modulus E _t (GPa)	Poisson ratio ν_t	Elongation e _t (%)	Tensile strength σ_u (MPa)
SMC 1	13.1	0.27	1.5	92
SMC 2	12.9	0.29	1.5	111
SMC3	13.8	0.39	1.4	120
SMC 4	14.5	0.29	1.7	166
Polyamide 1	9.1	0.37	1.9	135
Polyamide 2	7.7	0.23	1.8	93

Table 2. Tensile properties

The astonishing behaviour of both polyamides could be explained by the anisotropic behaviour of these composites: specimens of polyamide 35 were tested along the molding flow direction but the ones of polyamide 50 along the transverse direction.

3. R-CURVES CHARACTERIZATION

The fracture mechanics properties were determined using single edge notched bending specimens (SENB) with the following standard dimensions: 75 mm long, 17 mm wide and with a relative notch length to specimen width ratio, a/W , of 0.3. The notch was made by means of a very thin diamond disc, which assures a fixed root radius of 0.06 mm.

The experimental conditions of the fracture mechanics tests were selected according to the standard protocol recommended by the European Group of Fracture for determining the fracture toughness of plastics (2). During the three-points bending tests a substantial amount of crack growth was always recorded prior to the attainment of the maximum load, visualized by a non-linear relationship on the load-displacement graphic. So these materials are not well characterized by means of single parameters such as fracture toughness or fracture energy at initiation or at instability, and it is convenient to describe the whole crack growth when loaded until instability is attained. So, methods that account for stable crack growth, such as the Resistance curves (R-curves), are most suitable.

The damage growth from the acute notches during the loading of the specimens is difficult to evaluate by means of microscopic techniques unless an equivalent crack length is obtained since a damage zone of a size difficult to evaluate is always produced in front of the notch. Figures 1 and 2 show the different damage micromechanisms present respectively during the crack growth of SMCs and polyamides. Phenomena like crack branching, debonding, fibre pull-out and also, in the case of polyamides, matrix plastic deformation are clearly seen.

Figure 1. Surface damage on SMCs

Figure 2. Surface damage on Polyamides (66x)

3.1. R-curves determination

Two methods were used in order to determine the R-curves of these materials using different techniques in order to obtain a fictitious crack which has a similar compliance to the damaged specimen (3,4). The first one relies on the obtainment of an equivalent crack length based on a direct estimation of the specimen compliance from the continuous load-displacement plot of each test, based on drawing a straight line from the origin to any point on that curve. This method assumes that all the non-linearity observed on the plot is due to the damage growth. The second method is a more

accurate one, as the specimens are unloaded and reloaded at regular intervals, and so the true specimen compliance is evaluated.

The relative crack growth $\Delta a/a$ is related to the specimen compliance by means of the following relationship:

$$\frac{\Delta a}{a} = \frac{\Phi \Delta C}{(a/W)C}$$

where Φ is the energy calibration factor given in (2).

The stress intensity factor K was always calculated using the isotropic factor of the tested geometry (2).

Figure 3 compares the two methods described to obtain the R-curves with two SMC materials. There is not any important difference between them as all the points are located inside the same dispersion band.

Fig.3. a) SMC2

Fig 3. b) SMC4

Figure 3. Comparison between the methods used to determine the R-curves.a) SMC 2, b) SMC 4

3.2. Influence of testing factors on the R-curves characterization

During recent years, several studies reporting the experimental factors which could influence the toughness results on short-fibre reinforced composites have been published (5,6,7). The different results are not sufficiently consistent, and so greater effort is still necessary in this field.

In the present work, we have studied the influence of the initial crack length and acuity, the specimen size and the weight fibre fraction on the R-curves of our composites.

Figure 4 describes the effect of the initial crack length on the R-curve behaviour of an SMC and a glass reinforced polyamide. We have always used the same geometry but we have modified the relative size of the notch, a/W , between 0.1 and 0.5. It can be clearly seen that we have not found in either case any important differences among our results: all the corresponding points lie within the same dispersion band.

Fig.4. a) SMC2

Fig.4. b) Polyamide 1

Figure 4. Influence of crack length on R-curves. a) SMC2, b) Polyamide 1

Figure 5 shows the effect of the root radius of the notch. In this case we have used the standard diamond disc ($r=0.06$ mm) and a thicker disc which assures a root radius of 0.32 mm. The obtained results are perfectly comparable with a very low dispersion.

Figure 5. Influence of root notch radius on R-curves, SMC-2.

Figure 6 presents the influence of the specimen size on these tests. We have modified all the specimen dimensions (all are related to the width) when using specimen widths of 12 mm to compare with the results which had been obtained with the standard specimen width of 17mm. Both results lie within a very narrow band.

Figure 6. Influence of specimen size on R-curves, polyamide 2.

Finally, Figure 7 shows the results obtained with the different SMC, whose most important differences were, as can be seen in Table 1, the % weight fraction. The R-curves move to higher K values when the glass fibre weight fraction increases.

Figure 7. Influence of glass fibre weight fraction on R-curves, SMCs.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical behaviour of short fibre reinforced polymer composites in the presence of notches is best characterized by means of the R-curves as a stable crack growth always develops before the catastrophic failure of the specimen. The R-curve in these materials is an intrinsic property as it has been proved that it does not depend on the crack length, acuity nor on the size of the specimen. Only the fibre weight fraction has an influence: the R-curves, and also the tensile properties, increase when the fibre weight fraction grows.

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